

Abhandlung

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The Late Babylonian Series of ‘Ancient Sumerian’: Structure, Contents, and the Agency of Ritual Texts

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Abstract: In this article, we shed new light on the series with the emic title ‘Ancient Sumerian’, previously known from the Late Babylonian ritual texts for the New Year Festival. We first establish a new reading of the title, the key to which lies in a Late Babylonian pseudepigraphic letter. Following that, we present the contents of the series, including the edition of the hitherto unpublished tablet BM 32544+ that according to its colophon belongs to the series. Finally, we discuss the possible purposes of the series in its Late Babylonian context, where ritual in its written form took on an unprecedented role in the temple cult.

1 Introduction

By the Hellenistic period, Sumerian had not been spoken colloquially for almost two thousand years, although it was still heard on a daily basis in ritual contexts.¹ To the Babylonians of that time, it was clear that this was an ancient language which held a special status and importance, both in its study and in its use. Meanwhile, the existence of the traditional Babylonian cult itself came under threat, as Babylonia was integrated into larger empires ruled by kings who did not care for the gods of Babylon. It is in this context that a new corpus of cuneiform cultic texts was created that was gathered within a series called ‘Ancient Sumerian’. This series was previously known from the colophons of two Hellenistic ritual texts that provide rituals to be performed at the New Year (NYF texts).² However, the exact nature of

this series remains obscure and its creation in this late age of cuneiform culture raises many questions.

In this article, we aim to reach a better understanding of the particularities of the Late Babylonian series called ‘Ancient Sumerian’.³ We begin by establishing the reading of the series’ title in light of what we consider a reference to it in a Late Babylonian pseudepigraphic letter. Next, we present the edition of BM 32544+, a previously unpublished text which according to its colophon belongs to the series ‘Ancient Sumerian’. Then follows an overview of the structure and contents of ‘Ancient Sumerian’, which must have included a minimum of twenty-four tablets of which only a handful have been preserved. This dire state of preservation makes it difficult to determine the exact contents and purposes of ‘Ancient Sumerian’, but we will make some suggestions in the final sections of this paper. As we will show, ‘Ancient Sumerian’ is inextricably connected to its context of creation: the priestly community of Late Babylonian Babylon’s Esaġil.

¹ This is especially the case with the *kalātu* repertoire, consisting of Sumerian (Emesal) texts, which formed a significant part of the temple cult (see Gabbay 2014). The abbreviations used in this article follow those listed in the Reallexikon der Assyriologie.

² DT 15 and BM 32484+DT 114 respectively; see Debourse 2022a, 94–137; Linssen 2004, 215–237; Hunger 1968, no. 182: 65–66; Thureau-Dangin 1921, 127–154.

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³ We use “Late Babylonian” to refer to the period from 484 BCE until the end of cuneiform writing (80 CE). The exact dating of the texts belonging to ‘Ancient Sumerian’ cannot be determined, but should most likely be placed in the Hellenistic period (late 4th–early 2nd centuries BCE; see Debourse 2022a, 177–336).

2 The series ‘Ancient Sumerian’: eme-gi₇ ul-e or eme-gi₇ ul-dù-a

BM 45642, a tablet from Babylon dating to the Seleucid period, contains a copy of a letter by the scholars of the city of Borsippa to the Assyrian king Ashurbanipal (Frame and George 2005, 265–270). As has been shown by previous scholarship, this and similar letters, are not copies of actual letters dating to the time of Ashurbanipal, but are rather pseudo-epigraphic texts that reflect the Babylonian priestly ideology in the Seleucid period.⁴ The tablet in question deals with the transfer of texts from the scholars of Borsippa to Ashurbanipal’s libraries in Nineveh. The scholars of Borsippa promise the king they will work hard to copy on wooden writing boards all the scholarly lore, and send them to Assyria. Yet, then they mention one single text that they will not be able to copy and send to the king. This passage was transliterated and translated by the editors of the letter as following (Frame/George 2005, 269):

ù ana UGU ^šDA šá EME.GI₇ (UD).UL.DÙ.A / šá taš-pu-ru al-la šá ina é-sag-gil ia-a-nu en-ni ina IGI LUGAL EN-ni lim-šal / [lu] ‘ta’-[š]ap-pa-ra-am-ma a-na ^lDUMU.MEŠ E^{ki}

“But regarding the board in Sumerian, the glossary (^šDA šá EME.GI₇ (UD).UL.DÙ.A) about which you sent word, there is none but that in the Esağil temple (of Babylon). Let enquiries now be made before our lord the king, and you should send word to the citizens of Babylon”. (obv. 12–14)

According to this translation, there was a Sumerian *glossary* that could only be found in the Esağil temple of Babylon and was not available elsewhere. The questions then arise of what this glossary could include and why it was so unique that it does not appear anywhere besides in the Esağil temple. Frame and George (2005, 277) suggested to connect this “Sumerian glossary” with one that is mentioned in another literary letter (BM 28825 rev. 5, see Frame/George 2005, 274: 27), but the identification in that letter is questionable as well (see n. 6 below). In any case, there is no clear reason why the letter would emphasize that a specific glossary could not be found anywhere but the Esağil temple. In addition, the reference to the text as a “board in Sumerian, the glossary” is awkward both syntactically and stylistically.⁵

⁴ Frahm 2005; Goldstein 2010; Jursa/Debourse 2020. Note that Frahm argues for the presence of a historical kernel in these compositions.

⁵ Note that in his famous letter to the Assyrian king SAA 10, 160, the Babylonian *kalû* priest and scholar Marduk-šāpik-zēri refers to one of his colleagues (rev. 2) as mastering UD.UL.DÙ.A *pa-ni u šu-me-ri*, “ancient and Sumerian lists”.

In fact, to arrive at this reading, the editors had to emend the text and add a sign (UD), assuming that a scribal mistake had omitted it.

Therefore, we propose a radically different understanding of this passage, one that does not require emendation of the text. We suggest that this is not a reference to an obscure glossary, but rather that this important text which is available only in Esağil is none other than the series that also contains the New Year Festival texts – the series called ‘Ancient Sumerian’, which is usually read eme-gi₇ ul-e, but which should probably be revised to eme-gi₇ ul-dù-a, as will be explained immediately below.

Thus, we suggest that the passage from the letter cited above, which supposedly mentions a glossary, should in fact be translated:

“But regarding the board of ‘Ancient Sumerian’ (^šDA šá eme-gi₇ ul-dù-a) about which you sent word, there is none but that in the Esağil temple”.⁶

If indeed eme-gi₇ ul-dù-a refers to the same ‘Ancient Sumerian’ series known from the colophons of the NYF texts, this would supposedly not agree with the name of the series known from the colophons of the tablets of the NYF

⁶ A text that may contest our suggestion is BM 28825, a (pseudepigraphic) letter similar to BM 45642, but probably addressed to Ashurbanipal from the scholars of Babylon (rather than from the scholars of Borsippa in BM 45642) (see Frame/George 2005, 270–277). This text mentions (rev. 5), in a broken context what was read and translated by the editors of the tablet as: [...] UD.UL.DÙ.A e n [b]e-[l]u? TA ‘é’-sağ-il ina UGU ^šDA šá ^šMES.MÁ.GAN-nu šá x [x x], “[...] The glossary e n = *bēlu* from Esangil, on a writing board of sissoo-wood that [...]” (Frame/George 2005, 274–275: 27). This could supposedly indicate the mention of a glossary (UD.UL.DÙ.A = *šātu*) in the context of the Esağil, perhaps indicating that this should be the case in BM 45642 too. However, it should be noted that there are several problems with this reading and interpretation: First, according to the photograph published by Frame/George (2005, 271), the first sign in the passage cited from BM 28825 is quite broken, and UD is not entirely certain on the tablet (although admittedly it does seem preferable to the end of KU in e m e - g i₇); and second, such a lexical list is not known (although see the suggestion by A. Cavigneaux *apud* Frame/George 2005, 277), and it is unclear why this specific text would be mentioned here. If the text should actually be read [eme]-^lgi₇²¹ ul-dù-a, then it would again be clear why it is mentioned with the Esağil (the following EN could stand here for *adi*, “with”, and the following two signs are unclear). Alternatively, it is possible that ^lUD²¹ UL.DÙ.A here simply refers to “former days,” perhaps even general ancient texts to be copied on writing boards, and not to a specific glossary or to the ‘Ancient Sumerian’ series; note that three lines further in the text, in line rev. 8, there is reference to “scribal lore from former days”, see Frame/George 2005, 274: 30 (reading TA U₄-mu IGL.MEŠ as *ultu ūmi pānūti*; we thank Tonio Mitto for this suggestion).

texts, which was usually read as *eme-gi₇ ul-e*.⁷ Although the meaning would not be very different (both would still mean ‘Ancient Sumerian’; both *ul* and *ul-dù-a* correspond to *šātu*, “distant time, ancient”; for a discussion of the implications of this meaning, see section 5 below), and although it is possible that some corruption occurred in the transmission of this name because the sign E is similar in form to the combination of the signs DÙ and A, we would like to suggest that the reading in the colophons may actually be revised, since in all three manuscripts that refer to this series, the end of the name of the series is quite broken. See the overview, including new collation drawings, in section 5 below.

Thus, the letter from the scholars of Borsippa to the king Ashurbanipal seems to refer to the same *eme-gi₇ ul-dù-a* (‘Ancient Sumerian’) series attested on the colophons of tablets from Babylon. This implies that in the letter, the scholars of Borsippa state that they did not have access to the series ‘Ancient Sumerian’, a text that was specifically associated with the *Esağil* temple, both in content – it deals with the rituals of the *Esağil* temple – but also, as we will argue below, in the placement of the physical objects on which the texts in this series were written – they were found only in the *Esağil*. In the following, we will discuss the content of this series, starting with the edition of a new text belonging to the series *eme-gi₇ ul-dù-a*, ‘Ancient Sumerian’.

3 Edition of BM 32544+

The two fragments, BM 32544 (1877-11-17, 2286)⁸ and BM 32644 (18-76-1117, 2410),⁹ joined by A. R. George and I. Finkel, were hitherto never published, although they were known to various scholars over the years. Preliminary and partial transliterations (all unpublished) were prepared by W. G. Lambert (Folio 19555) and A. R. George (Folios 278–279), and a preliminary digital transliteration was prepared by members of the Electronic Babylonian Library (eBL) project.¹⁰

BM 32544+BM 32644 (measurements: 8.2 × 14.2 cm), most probably comes from Babylon and dates to the Hel-

lenistic period. Only the bottom part of one side of the tablet is preserved, which according to the catchline and secrecy formula is to be identified as the reverse (although the surface is mostly flat, which would otherwise indicate the obverse of a tablet). None of the edges are preserved, but presumably little is lost at the left-hand side of the tablet, and probably also in the well-preserved parts of the right-hand side of the tablet. The tablet seems to have contained one column of text, with rather long lines.

Based on paleography the tablet can be securely dated to the Hellenistic period (4th–2nd centuries BCE), with typical sign forms such as the slanted MEŠ and “open” signs like NAG.¹¹ On the other hand, compared to other Late Babylonian manuscripts, the signs seem to be less slanted and have longer, straighter verticals (note, for example, the boxed KI in line 8). The orthography in which the text is written, especially the heavy logographic writings (see below), also point towards a late dating of the tablet.

The manuscript contains a few different sections of text: the first eight lines consist of a bilingual text with pairs of Sumerian and Akkadian lines. Then follows a subscript to the bilingual text, after which come the tablet’s colophon, a catchphrase, and a secrecy formula.

Generally, as will be discussed immediately below and in sections 4–5 below, the text in the tablet agrees with many features known from other NYF texts of the ‘Ancient Sumerian’ series, including the language (Sumerian, Akkadian, bilingual), phraseology, orthography, content, and other features (such as the focus on the *aḫu-rabû* priest, the time of the ritual, and on the written nature of the text, see section 6 below). Since the NYF texts have been shown by Debourse (2022a, 91–93, 179–244) to date to the Seleucid period, the composition on BM 32544+ (and not only the tablet itself) should also be dated to this period (although it cannot be excluded that it also made use of earlier materials).

The bilingual text poses some challenges, as the connection between the Sumerian and Akkadian lines is mostly not directly apparent. This is in line with other bilingual passages, said to be recited during the New Year festival and belonging to the series ‘Ancient Sumerian’, in which the sense of the Sumerian text is difficult to interpret and which can only sporadically be linked to the Akkadian version of the line (Debourse 2022a, 196–200).¹²

⁷ The element *ul*, “ancient”, was read as *du₇*, “perfect” by Linssen (2004, 218. 227, line 216a. 224. 233 line 472); for the reading *ul*, “ancient”, see Debourse (2022a, 114–115).

⁸ Leichty et al. 2019, 148: “Bilingual prayer; tablet XX of *eme-gi₇* (cf. Thureau-Dangin, *Rituels accadiens*, p. 150 vi 28)”.
⁹ Leichty et al. 2019, 152: “*Esangila* ritual”.

¹⁰ See <https://www.ebl.lmu.de/fragmentarium/BM.32544> (A. Heinrich, E. Jiménez, J. Taniguchi, T. Mitto) (last accessed: 25.12.22). We thank A. George and E. Jiménez who encouraged us to publish the text.

¹¹ The closing upper horizontal wedge is omitted. Debourse 2022a, 179–181; <https://labasi.acdh.oeaw.ac.at> (last accessed 19.06.2022).

¹² As noted by Debourse (2022a, 197–199), the relationship between the Sumerian and Akkadian text does not seem to be a sophisticated and highly scholarly one as is known from other bilingual texts (e. g.,

BM 32544

BM 32644

The orthography of the Akkadian lines is at times heavily logographic, using also relatively rare logograms (such as BI for the first element of the possessive suffix *-šun(u)* or SAG.MAš in ll. 6' and 8').¹³ Such cases are also found in other texts in the ‘Ancient Sumerian’ series.¹⁴

The non-standard bilingual nature of the text, and the orthography of the Akkadian text, leads to some difficulties in understanding the text, and we have to emphasize that some of our readings are conjectural.

The content of the bilingual text is not easy to grasp. Due to its bilingual nature and because of its place in the

cultic series of ‘Ancient Sumerian’, we would expect it to be a prayer. However, the preserved text does not read like a prayer: there is no invocation of a deity, no praise, no petition. Instead, the text has some narrative qualities, being reminiscent of an origin myth. According to its Akkadian translation it seems to deal with the establishment of privileges for the “sons of Babylon” by the god Bēl. The subscript, moreover, states that this text was written on the Dais of Destinies of Bēl, most probably in the Eşaġil temple, and consisted of sixteen lines, and thus our tablet which preserves four bilingual lines, contains the last quarter of this text.

The following line then designates the tablet as the 20th tablet of the series ‘Ancient Sumerian’, followed by a catchline to the next tablet, dealing with the rituals of the first day of Nisannu. This is followed by the beginning of a “secrecy” label.

George 2009, 78–112; Jacobsen 1991; Veldhuis 2018; Baragli 2022; see Mitto, forthcoming). Rather, the relationship between the two versions seems more flexible, with only a few specific lexical correspondences, and therefore the Akkadian text seems to be an interpretation of the Sumerian text as a whole, even if the specific details do not seem to have clear lexical anchors known from elsewhere (for a similar phenomenon, compare the bilingual Nanāya syncretistic hymn known from Assyrian and Babylonian tablets, see Oshima 2020). Note other non-standard bilingual and code-switching features in this series, such as the transfer from Sumerian or Sumerian-Akkadian passages to monolingual Akkadian passages in the same text, or the mixing of Sumerian and Akkadian phrases in the same lines (see DT 15 i 5–32 and MNB 1848 ii 31–iii 33, see Debourse 2022a, 95. 139–140).

¹³ This is usually uncommon in Akkadian translations of Sumerian texts, which, due to their nature as glosses, tend to be more syllabic.

¹⁴ See, e. g., DT 15 i 5–14 (in bilingual context), ii 20–21 (unilingual Akkadian context), see Debourse 2022a, 95–96.

Transliteration

- 1' [x x x x] 'x' []
 2' [x x] 'URU²¹-šú-nu NU È 'KÚR¹ NU 'i-kab-ba-su' []
 ([...] *ālišunu ul uššū nakrū lā ikabbasū* [...])
 3' [x (x)] 'x¹-zi-da nu-ġál ér nu-ġíd-ġíd-en []
 4' [^{dE}N² NAM-šú-nu-tú NAM KUR ana DINGIR u LUGAL šùD u NAM []
 ([^{dBē}] *išāmšunūti šimat māti ana ili u šarri ikribu u ...* [...])
 5' [lugal] ĠIR.NÍTA ġiš tuk-tuk-e-ne mas-su-bi mas-su-ra []
 6' *šar-ri u ĠIR.NÍTA NU UŠ-šú-nu-ti 'GÚ²¹ BAR²-tú NU LÁ-aš EGIR-su₁₅(BI)-^fun x¹ [ubān lemutti(?)]*
 (*šarru u šakkanakku ul immidūšunūti biltu aḫītu lā ittarrašū arkīšun [ubān lemutti]*)
 7' [lugal]-e dumu ^ddu-šar-ra ġiš nu-ġál šu-a-bi-dil-e-ne ġiš nu-naġ x []
 8' LUGAL šá DUMU.MEŠ E^{ki} GAR-an SAG.MAŠ-su₁₅(BI)-^fun¹ E-bi I-šú₁₃-un *ú-šar-ba-a ana d[ar² zikiršun(u)](?)*
 (*šarru ša mārē bābili išakkan ašarēdūssun iqabbi tanittašun ušarbā ana [dār zikiršun(u)](?)*)
-
- 9' (vacat) 16 MU.ŠID.BI šá UGU BÁRA NAM.'MEŠ¹ ša ^dEN [šatrū](?)
-
- 10' 'IM.DUB¹ 20.KAM.MA eme-ġi₇ [ul-dù]-^fa¹ NU A[L.TI]L² I[M.DUB šá EGIR-šú](?)
-
- 11' [(DIŠ) ina ⁱuBÁ]R UD.'1'.[KAM NO. DANNA](?) GE₆ ⁱuš[ES-GAL ZI-ma A.MEŠ ^f]IDIGNA [^dBURANUN.(KI) TU₅]
-
- 12' [pa-liḫ ^dAMAR.UTU u ^dzar-pa-ni-tu₄ ana šU^{II}] NU È ma-diš 'ú²¹-[šur(?) ...]
 Perhaps one more broken line before end of tablet

Translation (according to the Akkadian version)

- 1'–2' They do not come out [from](?) their city(?); enemies do not suppress [...],
 3'–4' [Bēl](?) decrees for them the fate of the land; to the god and king, prayer and ... [...],
 5'–6' King and governor do not impose a foreign tribute on them; [a finger of evil](?) is not stretched after them.
 7'–8' The king – regarding the citizens of Babylon, he establishes their prominence, he speaks their praise, he magnifies [their name](?) for[ever](?).
-
- 9' 16 lines total which are [written](?) on the Dais of Destinies of Bēl.
-
- 10' Tablet 20 (of) “[Ancie]nt Sumerian”. Not com[plete]d. The ta[blet following it]:(?)
-
- 11' [In the month Nisan]nu on the first day [at N double-hours](?) of the night, the El[der Brother will rise and wash with water from the] Tigris and [Euphrates].
-
- 12' [He who reveres Marduk and Zarpānītu] should not make it available (to others)! Gu[ard (it)](?) very much!(?) [...].
 13' []
 Rest broken

Notes

3'–4'. There is no clear correspondence between the Sumerian and Akkadian lines, except perhaps for Sumerian *ér*, “lament, prayer”, corresponding to *šùD*, “prayer”, in the Akkadian line (perhaps standing for *ikribu*, although *ér* is not otherwise equated with *ikribu*, but with *takribtu* and *unnīnu*).

Note that the Sumerian negations are not reflected in the Akkadian version (also in lines 7'–8'), a phenomenon that seems to occur in other texts belonging to the ‘Ancient Sumerian’ series (DT 15 i 9–10, DT 114 i 8–9, perhaps also 12–17, see Debourse 2022a, 95. 116, cf. 122). Note that in all these occurrences *nu-* seems to correspond to Akkadian participles (perhaps as a form of *lú?*), but this is not the case in our line.

4'. Since the signs KUR and TIN can be very similar in Late Babylonian paleography, one cannot rule out the possibility to read NAM TIN (i. e., *šimat balāṭi*, “fate of life”).¹⁵ At the end of the line perhaps restore NAM.[ŠITA] (probably standing for a form of *karābu*, referring either to a type of prayer, or to a priest performing the prayer; see CAD I, 62; CAD K, 216) (suggestions: T. Mitto). Note the absence of an oblique wedge between or underneath the verticals of the sign NAM (appearing three times in this line; compare also in line 9').

5'–6'. Besides the first two nouns, there is no apparent correspondence between the Sumerian and Akkadian lines (although *ḡiš* in the Sumerian line can theoretically refer to the “load,” *biltu*, mentioned in the Akkadian line). The Sumerian line, if read independently from the Akkadian, would seem to mean: “The king and governor listen, their leader(?), to a leader(?) [...]”

6'. The Akkadian line, according to our restorations and understanding, contains two idiomatic expressions: *bilta emēdu* (CAD E, 142; here in the plural: *immidūšunūti*) and *ubāna tarāšu* (CAD T, 211; here in the N stem). In the continuation of the line, we thank T. Mitto for suggesting to read the sign BI as *-su₁₅* (as part of the possessive plural suffix, also in line 8').

7'–8'. In these lines, as in the previous ones, there is no clear correspondence between the Sumerian and Akkadian versions, besides the first few nouns. The correspondence *du-šar-ra* = Babylon is not known to us from anywhere else (unless Babylon in the Akkadian version actually corresponds to the following Sumerian phrase *ḡiš nu-ḡál*, for which compare *šu ḡiš-ḡál-la* that perhaps stands for Babylon in DT 15 i 15–16, see Debourse 2022a, 95). For *šu-a-bi-dil-e-ne*, compare *šu-a ab-dil-e-ne* (with variant: *šu-a-bi-dil-e-ne*) in the end of the Sumerian lines in the bilingual Nanāya hymn (where, as in our text, there is no straightforward correspondence between the Sumerian and Akkadian lines), perhaps meaning “they are one”, or “they are the same” (Oshima 2020, 372–377, with notes in p. 339, n. 15, and p. 378). Note that in the Nanāya hymn this phrase may also correspond to Akkadian *qabū* (Oshima 2020, 378), in which case the form in our line may correspond to the Akkadian E in line 8', probably standing for *iqabbi*. For the end of the Sumerian line, compare *ḡiš-naḡ* in BM 41577 iii 18 (Debourse 2022a, 161; in unilingual Sumerian context).

The syntactical structure beginning with *ša* and a genitive and followed by nouns with possessive suffixes, occurs

also in some prayers in the NYF texts, e. g. in the line: *ša DUMU.MEŠ E^{ki}ÉRIN ki-din-nu šu-kun šu-bar-ru-šu-nu* (DT 15 i 32; Debourse 2022a, 95. 100–101).

We tentatively understand SAG.MAŠ as *ašarēdu* or *ašarēdūtu*, usually written SAG.KAL, but once equated with the sequence BAD.KASKAL with the pronunciation sag-maš (Ea II:95, MSL 14, 251), and also equated sometimes with *máš-saḡ* (see references in CAD A/II, 416). The sign I is understood as a noun related to the verb *nādu*, “to praise”, which can be written (standing for a stative form in personal names) with the sign I (a noun such as *tanittu* would be expected in our line, but it is otherwise not written with I).

The restorations at the end of the line are tentative. It is possible that *šumšun* (compare CAD R, 49b) or a different noun should be restored.

9'. The sign before ⁴EN is read here as *ša*, although this is remarkable, since Late Babylonian texts consistently use *ša*. Moreover, the sign does not look like a typical *ša*, having a specific position of the two oblique wedges.

10'. The restorations of the specific signs at the end of the line are tentative, and are based on formulas found in the colophon of DT 114+ rev. vi 1'–2' (Debourse 2022a, 117), cited below section 5.

11'. The catchphrase cited here is longer than those in the colophons of the other NYF texts, which simply refer to (DIŠ) *ina* ITI.BÁR UD NO. KAM. The restoration [N DANNA] GE₆ is based on texts such as the incipit of DT 15: [(DIŠ)] *ina* ITI.BÁR UD 2.KAM 1 DANNA GE₆ (Debourse 2022a: 95: 1); but perhaps restore simply [*ina*] GE₆ (cf. DIŠ *ina* ITI.BÁR UD 1.KAM *ina še-rim* in Çaḡırgan 1976, 13; see below section 5).

12'. Compare the colophon of DT 114+: *pa-liḡ⁴AMAR.UTU u⁴zar-pa-ni-tu₄ ana šu^{II} NU È šá ana šu^{II} È-u DINGIR.DINGIR ma-la ina qé-reb^{uruEki} ba-šu-u li-ru-ru-šu*, “He who reveres Marduk and Zarpānitu should not make (it) available (to others); he who makes (it) available (to others) may the gods, as many as there are in Babylon, curse him” (Debourse 2022a, 117). The available space in the beginning of the line would fit such a reconstruction. However, the continuation of the phrase does not seem to agree with the signs in our line, which we read as *ma-diš¹ur¹-[sur]*, a phrase appearing in other Late Babylonian colophons (compare Hunger 1968, nos. 170–171), and most notably, in another New Year ritual text, BM 41577 rev. iv 21', see Debourse 2022a, 162. 168–169.

4 Content of BM 32544+

The bilingual text in BM 32544+ deals with the privileged status of the citizens of Babylon (*mārē Bābili*), seemingly granted to them by Bēl. Although it is only implicit in these

¹⁵ Compare images of KUR and TIN on https://labasi.acdh.oew.ac.at/browsing/signs-compare/?sign_first=DIN&sign_second=KUR (last accessed 16.02.2023).

last four preserved lines, Bēl offers the Babylonians divine protection against enemies and bad kingship, decreeing a good fate for the city of Babylon. Remarkably, this text is said to be written on the Dais of Destinies. In Neo-Babylonian royal inscriptions, this cultic installation is conceived of as the location where the fate of king and country were decided by the divine assembly during the *akītu*-festival.¹⁶ The present text, however, does not concern the destiny of the king at all, but that of the “sons of Babylon”. This is an important discursive shift, focusing the attention on the Babylonians and not on the figure of the king as would be expected. This is further emphasized by the last line of the bilingual text. Here, the king is described as confirming the privileged status of the Babylonians in terms that are usually reserved for the reverence of kings or gods: he “speaks their praise” and “magnifies their name”. The use of this language and what it expresses seemingly elevates the “sons of Babylon” above the king, who himself must submit to the will of Bēl and grant them this status. In other words, we have here a reversal of what could be considered “traditional Babylonian” roles, in which the “sons of Babylon” are the chosen ones of Bēl, not the king.

This exceptional prominence of the “sons of Babylon” clearly fits the context of the Late Babylonian Priestly Literature (Debourse 2022a, 399–403; Jursa/Debourse 2020). This late branch of cuneiform writings was created under foreign rule (Persian, Hellenistic, Parthian), i. e., at a time when the native Babylonian king was absent. It deals largely with priestly matters both in a cultic sense (the continuity and correct observation of ritual worship) and a socio-political sense (the temple’s relation with imperial powers). In essence, these texts serve to confirm the identity of the Babylonian priests who had to deal with the changing circumstances in which they found themselves (Debourse 2022a, 401–404). They do this by developing several motifs that emphasize the prominence of the priesthood, be it as guardians of cuneiform lore, protectors of the cult, or advisors to (non-native) kings.

The priestly protagonists are also contrasted with the person of the king. While the priests are divinely chosen and fall naturally under the protection of Bēl, the king does not automatically receive divine favor: he is required to humble himself and show due reverence to the gods who are to accept his rule. The NYF texts, which are part of the Late Babylonian Priestly Literature, are exemplary of this dynamic between priest, king, and god that is so

defining for this corpus (Debourse 2022a). The portrayal of priest and king respectively crystallizes in the episode of the ritual humiliation and negative confession of the king, which depicts the priest as a powerful agent and the king as passive participant in a rite of royal confirmation.¹⁷

In the bilingual text in BM 32544+, this relation between priest and king is transposed to the collective level. Here, it is the *mārē Bābili* who are collectively elevated above the king. Reading BM 32544+ in the context of the NYF texts helps us to understand that these “sons of Babylon” are not just citizens of Babylon, but a specific group of people connected to the temple and its deity (Debourse 2022a: 321–323). The privileged status of these sons of Babylon, referred to in BM 32544+, is also a prominent topic in the NYF texts. There we find explicit references to the *kidinnūtu* of the Babylonians, who are described as *šābē kidinni* (Debourse 2022a, 321–327; Pongratz-Leisten 1997).

Finally, note that there are a few direct textual connectors between BM 32544+ and the NYF texts. As described in the commentary above, the phrasing of line 8’ is reminiscent of a recurrent phrase in the recitations of the NYF texts. The mention of “king and governor” (5’) reoccurs in the NYF texts too (DT 15 v 179; BM 32655 ii 14’ and 16’).¹⁸ Additionally, as discussed in section 3 above, the non-standard bilingual features of the prayer are also found in passages of the NYF texts. Aside from that, the catchphrase is identical to the ones used in the NYF texts, and BM 32544+ makes use of the same paratextual notes (see commentary above). Furthermore, both BM 32544+ and the NYF texts are (implicitly) concerned with the New Year, the former by means of its reference to the decreeing of destinies and the Dais of Destinies, as well as the catchline referring to the first day of Nisannu, and the latter by its chronological setting at the beginning of Nisannu.¹⁹ Finally, the NYF texts and BM 32544+ are all part of the same series of ‘Ancient Sumerian’, as will be discussed below.

¹⁶ Nebuchadnezzar II’s “East India House Inscription”: Sackler Nbk obv. ii 64–iii 18 (Wallenfels 2008, 280–281, 290–291) // ST ii 54–iii 12 (Langdon 1912, 124–127).

¹⁷ MNB 1848 vi 29–42 (Debourse 2022a, 142. 154–155) and BM 32485+ vi 1–12 (Debourse 2022a, 126. 132–133); see also Debourse 2019.

¹⁸ See Debourse 2022a, 97. 106–107. 174–175. Note also Lambert folio 019544, containing a reading of BM 32655, where he notes “cf. BM 32544?”, and similarly folio 019555, with BM 32544, where he refers to BM 32655.

¹⁹ Note that the NYF texts do not contain any mentions of “New Year” or “*akītu*”. For the decreeing of destinies at the Dais of Destinies during the New Year, see Pongratz-Leisten (1994, 56–65).

5 Structure and contents of the series ‘Ancient Sumerian’

BM 32544+ is labeled in its colophon as the 20th tablet of ‘Ancient Sumerian’. Only two other texts containing that label are known so far and they are part of the so-called NYF texts, which describe the rituals performed by the high

priest in Esaġil during the first days of Nisannu.²⁰ According to their colophons, these are the 22nd and 23rd tablets of ‘Ancient Sumerian’ respectively. While none of the other NYF texts have preserved colophons, they were presumably all part of the series ‘Ancient Sumerian’, considering their similarities. Below follows an overview of the paratextual notes that help us understand the structure and contents of ‘Ancient Sumerian’.²¹

Colophon of BM 32544+, rev. 10'–11'

ʿIM.DUB¹ 20.KAM.MA eme-gi₇ [ul-dù]-ʿa¹ NU A[L.T]I[?] I[M.DUB šá EGIR-šú](?)

[(DIŠ) ina ^{iti}BÁR UD ʿ1.[KAM NO. DANNA](?) GE₆ ^{luš}[EŠ-GAL ZI-ma A.MEŠ ⁱ]dIDIGNA ⁱ[dBURANUN.(KI) TU₅]²²

20th tablet (of) “[Ancie]nt Sumerian”. Not com[pleted]. Tablet that follows it: [“In the month Nisan]nu, on the first day [at N double-hours] of the night, the El[der Brother will rise and wash with water] from the Tigris and [Euphrates]”.

First line of Çaġırgan 1976, 13: no. 1; colophon not preserved

DIŠ ina ^{iti}BÁR UD 1.KAM ina še-rim ^{luš}ES![?]-G[AL![?]]

In the month Nisannu, on the first day in the evening, the El[der] Brother []

Note: Çaġırgan 19: 13 read the last signs as: ^{lu}mu-ba[n-nu]. But the *mubannû* official is not further mentioned in the fragment or in the NYF texts, and it is likely that the text should be emended to ^{luš}ES![?]-G[AL![?]].

Colophon of DT 15 rev. vi 28–29 (Debourse 2022a, 99)

IM 22.ʿKAM¹.MA eme-gi₇ ul-(dù)?-ʿa¹ NU ʿAL¹.TIL

IM šá EGIR-šú ina ^{iti}BÁR UD 4.KAM²³

22nd tablet of ‘Ancient Sumerian’. Not completed.

Tablet that follows this one: “In the month Nisannu, on the fourth day”.

Colophon of DT 114+ rev. vi 1'–3' (Debourse 2022a, 117)

²⁰ See footnote 2 above.

²¹ Line drawings are provided only of the lines that relate the series’ name, so as to illustrate our reading ul-dù-a instead of ul-e.

²² The sign after the break is a double vertical, which can fit both the end of E and the end of A. The width of the broken space supports the restoration of two signs ([ul-dù]-ʿa¹) rather than one ([ul]-ʿe¹).

²³ Of the three colophons mentioning the name of the series, this is the best preserved one. After the sign UL there is a break, after which

a double vertical is seen which can fit the end of both A and E. A small wedge mark at the very low part of the line after UL (not in Racc. copy; collated) would seem to support the bottom left part of DÙ rather than E. Admittedly, though, this would indicate that the sign DÙ is written in a very condensed way. We therefore follow a suggestion by an anonymous reviewer of this article that DÙ in this case could have been left out of the title and should therefore be emended in the text, but perhaps a different textual corruption occurred here.

ʿIM.DUB 23 eme-gi₇ ul-dù-a¹ [NU TI]
 IM.DUB šá EGIR-[šú]
 DIŠ ina iⁱⁱⁱBÁR UD 5.KAM IGI.TAB u IGI.KÁ[R]²⁴
 23rd tablet of “[Ancient] Sumerian”. [Not completed].
 Tablet that follows [this one]:
 “In the month Nisannu, on the fifth day”. Collated and checked.

Note on upper edge of MNB 1848 (Debourse 2022a, 138); no colophon preserved

ʿIM¹ šá EGIR-šú
 ʿDIŠ ina iⁱⁱⁱBÁR UD 5.KAM
 The tablet that follows this one:
 “In the month Nisannu on the fifth day”.

Subscripts to the prayers in BM 41577 (Debourse 2022a, 160–172; George 2000, 260–270); no colophon preserved

obv. iii 5; 21 *a-sa-ar ka-lu-tu*
 rev. iv 21' *a-sa-ar a-ši-pu-tu*

Subscript to the Eulogy on the Elder Brother = BM 32655 // BM 32374, lo.e. (Jursa/Debourse 2017, 90–91; see George/Taniguchi 2021, no. 449; George 2021; Debourse 2022a, 173–176); no colophon preserved

30 MU ŠID.BI šá ina UGU ʿIM¹.DUB ʿšá¹ na^a ʿel-me-šú¹
 šá lúŠEŠ-GAL É.UMUŠ.A
 30 lines total which are (written) on the amber tablet
 of the Elder Brother of Eumuša

BM 32544+, edited in this paper, is said to be the 20th tablet of the series of ‘Ancient Sumerian’. Moreover, it contains a catchline, from which it can be deduced that the (missing) 21st tablet dealt with the first day of Nisannu. Perhaps this 21st tablet is the one edited by Çağırhan, which indeed starts “on the first day of Nisannu”.²⁵ This cannot be checked, however, because the colophon is lost.²⁶ The second and third days of Nisannu are dealt with in the tablet designated as the 22nd of the series (DT 15). This text also includes a catchline referring to the fourth day. As expected, the 23rd tablet of the series (DT 114+) then deals with the fourth day, but its contents continue into the fifth day. The catchline on this tablet moreover refers to the next tablet as also dealing with the fifth day.²⁷ Thus, the rituals performed by the Elder

Brother on the fifth day of Nisannu were not contained in one, but in at least two tablets. BM 41577 most likely relates to the sixth or seventh day of Nisannu. Although its colophon is broken off, it is very probable that this tablet too belongs to the series of ‘Ancient Sumerian’. Finally, there is BM 32655, duplicated by BM 32374. Its close relation to the other NYF texts suggests that this text too had its place in the series of ‘Ancient Sumerian’, although no colophon is preserved to confirm this claim.²⁸

What unites the texts belonging to the series of ‘Ancient Sumerian’ most strongly is the fact that they are set within Esağil. In addition, the same topics and concerns underlie all texts, most prominently the problem of kingship and the prominence of the priesthood. Another remarkable feature relates to their formal and linguistic unity.²⁹ None of the texts in the series have known precursors, and most are

²⁴ Hardly anything can be seen of the signs after gi₇, and both ʿul-e¹ and ʿul-dù-a¹ are possible, with a slight preference towards ʿdù-a¹, since it is possible that the bottom slanted horizontal of dù can be seen (collated from photograph).

²⁵ A Late Babylonian ritual text from Borsippa (BM 40790) contains rituals for the first to eleventh day of Nisannu (Da Riva/Galetti 2018). However, this text does not belong to the series of ‘Ancient Sumerian’: its partly preserved colophon is different from the ones in the series. Also, its contents are very distinct from the other NYF texts (see Debourse 2022a, 84–85).

²⁶ Moreover, the whereabouts of this tablet nowadays are unknown, so it cannot be collated.

²⁷ Also MNB 1848, a partial duplicate of DT 114+, contains a note on the

upper edge referring to the following tablet dealing with the fifth day. MNB 1848 is slightly smaller than DT 114+, however, and contains some twenty lines less (see Debourse 2022a, Appendix A. 201–202).

²⁸ There are other texts that according to the language, style, form and content, may eventually turn out to belong to the ‘Ancient Sumerian’ series. Among these, the following bilingual tablets may be noted: BM 32631, BM 41190 (reference T. Mitto).

²⁹ See also Debourse 2022a, 91–92; George 2000, 261. The exception lies in the different tablet formats: in contrast to the other tablets that have multiple columns, BM 32544+ seems to have had only a single column of text with exceptionally long lines.

only known from single manuscripts dating to the Hellenistic period.³⁰ They make use of similar paratextual notes, such as the catchline, and share a concern for secrecy. All dating formulae in the series follow the same pattern, and other specific Akkadian stock phrases reappear throughout the corpus. Another common feature is the use of Sumerian, mostly in bilingual prayers in which it does not always correspond to the Akkadian in a straightforward manner, as is evidenced in BM 32544+ edited above, as well as in other texts belonging to this series (see Debourse 2022a, 196–200; see also section 3 above).

The use of the non-standard Sumerian can best be explained as a way of making the texts seem older than they are (even though, it is possible that at least some of these Sumerian texts, or parts of them, are indeed older than the series itself). Sumerian, after all, was closely associated with the Babylonian cult and many of the standard recitations, such as incantations, prayers, and laments, were conducted in Sumerian. Using that language would grant these newly created texts more legitimacy within that cult.³¹ Other such antiquarian and archaizing tendencies underlie the texts in the series, both in terms of the language they use and the rituals they contain (Debourse 2022a, 334–336). The clearest marker of this antiquarianism is the name of the series, ‘Ancient Sumerian’, itself. It is possible that these are simply the first two words of the incipit of the series. However, as the name of this series it is nonetheless significant, considering not only the many Sumerian recitations these texts include, but foremost their rather non-standard, and even obscure nature. With this title, the authors emphasized the series’ (construed) antiquity, which in turn lent it more authority.

A few suggestions have previously been made as to the content of the series of ‘Ancient Sumerian’ (see also Debourse 2022a, 213–216). Some have suggested that the series in its entirety, “if recovered, would cover the whole year, maybe ending with the rites of Nisan as the climax of the entire cultic year”.³² In that case, the 20th tablet may

have provided instruction for rituals taking place at the end of the twelfth month Addaru. The previous nineteen tablets then dealt with rituals observed between Ayyāru and Addaru. A problem with this interpretation, however, is its suggestion that the series ended with the New Year Festival. We would rather expect it to start with that cultic event at the beginning of the first month. In addition, we actually do have contemporary ritual texts that contain rituals to be performed during other months of the year; such as Kislīmu (Çağırğan/Lambert 1991–1993) and Simānu (George 2000, 270–280), but the phraseology and style of these ritual texts differ significantly from those of the NYF texts (see Debourse 2022a, 179–218 and above).³³ It is therefore unlikely that these ritual texts belonged together with the NYF texts to the same series, and thus they probably do not belong to the series ‘Ancient Sumerian’.

Another idea is that ‘Ancient Sumerian’ is a series concerning the New Year Festival specifically (see Linssen 2004, 215). This would mean that a minimum of twenty-three tablets were dedicated to this one ritual. Moreover, the first day is treated on the 21st tablet, which raises the question of what the twenty tablets that came before that dealt with. Specifically, it is unclear how to place the 20th tablet, edited here, within that interpretation. Did this tablet also contain rituals for the first day? We know that the rituals for the fifth day were spread over more than one tablet, so that is a possibility. Furthermore, the preserved fragment of BM 32544+ refers to the *parak šimāti*, a cultic structure that played a central role during the NYF.³⁴ Nevertheless, that does not explain the nineteen tablets that came before BM 32544+, and it is perhaps difficult to imagine that they all contained New Year’s rites for the first day of Nisannu. Aside from that, as pointed out in the notes on BM 32544+ above, the catchphrase referring to the first day is much longer than that in the NYF texts, which may indicate the start of a new (chronological) cycle.

Both these previous suggestions hold in common that they are based on a chronological, calendrical principle. However, other criteria may have determined the relation-

³⁰ With the exception of the ritual instructions for Nisannu day 5 (cf. footnote 27), which might have been a draft (see Debourse 2022a, 201–203) and BM 32655 // BM 32374.

³¹ The cuneiform tradition of the Late Achaemenid and Hellenistic periods is strongly marked by such antiquarianism in general; see Frahm 2002; Beaulieu 1992.

³² Da Riva/Galetti 2018, 193. See also Lambert 1989: 23–24. The suggestion of Lambert (1997, 72), repeated by Da Riva/Galetti, that BM 77028 should be considered part of the same series is unlikely. The colophon of that tablet refers to itself as the “25th of the series (ÉŠ.GĀR) of ^dEN [...]”, which does not parallel the colophons of the tablets belonging to the ‘Ancient Sumerian’ series. Moreover, BM 77028 is dedicated to Nabū

(NÍG.GA ^dNĀ), which makes it likely that its context was not Esağil as is the case for the ‘Ancient Sumerian’ series.

³³ Four further ritual texts deal with rituals for the New Year, but in our opinion, it seems unlikely that they belong to the ‘Ancient Sumerian’ series. BM 40790 and BM 40854+ (Da Riva/Galetti 2018) are of Late Babylonian date but deal with the gods of Borsippa, Nabū and Nanāya; see also Debourse 2022a, 84–85. BM 47902+ (Lambert 1997, 52–56) and BM 40757 (Da Riva 2022) seem earlier than the other NYF texts that do belong to the ‘Ancient Sumerian’ series, based on paleographic and linguistic grounds. See Debourse forthcoming.

³⁴ See footnote 19 above.

ship between the tablets in the series ‘Ancient Sumerian’. Most of the texts address a specific cultic agent, the Elder Brother (*aĥu-rabû*) of Esaġil. One may speculate whether the series included different recitations of the Elder Brother in different ritual occasions related to the Esaġil temple (not necessarily all determined by the calendar). Thus, for example, it is possible that the prayer of the Elder Brother (Jursa/Debourse 2017; Debourse 2022a, 173–176) was part of this series but not necessarily related to the New Year festival, and the same could be said of BM 32544+ edited above. However, below we will suggest to go even one step further. The series may have not only been a compilation of rituals and recitations that took part in the Esaġil in different calendrical and non-calendrical occasions by or in the presence of the Elder Brother priest. It may have rather, or also, been a spatial description of the Esaġil, not according to its architectural layout, but according to its ritual, and specifically its recitational activities.

6 Text in ritual, ritual in text

As discussed above, the series ‘Ancient Sumerian’ should be seen in the context of the antiquarianism so characteristic of Hellenistic cuneiform culture. Yet, the texts in this series are not simply recording ritual, and moreover, are not just passive repositories of antiquarian research. In fact, we would argue that these texts have a distinct agency; an agency that relates to the ritual process, the temple as a sacred space, and the cultic authority of the priesthood. One way to uncover this agency is by considering how ritual is textualized in this series, how it is materialized through text.

As already mentioned above, the scene of the ritual actions and recitations found in the compositions of ‘Ancient Sumerian’ is the Esaġil temple in Babylon. Aside from direct references to this temple, the texts are specked with mentions of locations within the temple compound, such as Eumuša, Eu’ul,³⁵ the Dais of Destinies, or the Great Courtyard. Moreover, they address a cultic agent directly connected to Esaġil: the Elder Brother (*aĥu-rabû*) of Eumuša, i. e., the cella of Marduk in Esaġil.³⁶ However, not just the rituals they contain, but also the manuscripts of ‘Ancient Sumerian’ themselves are related to Esaġil in their physical, written form. Several paratextual notes from the series indicate that the cuneiform tablets were copies of texts that

were inscribed physically within the temple, be it on architectural structures or on objects. According to its subscript, the Eulogy of the Elder Brother (BM 32655), for example, was engraved on an amber tablet (*tuppi ša elmešî*) belonging to the Elder Brother, who may have worn it during ritual performances in the temple (see above). The bilingual text in BM 32544+ edited here was supposedly inscribed on the Dais of Destinies, a fixed structure found in the temple courtyard. Other prayers in the series, found on BM 41577, are said to be “according to an *asarru*”, an Akkadian noun that specifically relates to a written inscription.³⁷ Thus, in the series of ‘Ancient Sumerian’ there is an emphasis on the *written* form of textuality in rituals, specifically in the recitations carried out in rituals, and this written form is inextricably connected to the Esaġil temple.

How should we conceptualize this physical presence of the texts of ‘Ancient Sumerian’ in the temple? The letter BM 45642, cited above, may contain some crucial clues. There it is said that “regarding the board (on which the series of) ‘Ancient Sumerian’ (is to be copied), there is none but that in the Esaġil temple (*alla ša ina Esaġil yānu*)” (obv. 13). This phrasing suggests that the text was bound to its written form in the Esaġil, and can otherwise not be accessed. In other words, in order to copy the text on a writing board (as the king has ordered), one must have access into the Esaġil. Perhaps we may take this literally and consider the idea that the ‘Ancient Sumerian’ text was literally inscribed onto the sanctuary space of Esaġil. As such, the series of ‘Ancient Sumerian’ may have been conceptualized as a reflection of liturgical texts that were inscribed onto Esaġil’s architecture. Its contents are then not per se ordered by a chronological but rather by a spatial principle.

In cuneiform culture, writing was often found on monumental architecture, such as palace walls and city gates. Temples too were physically pervaded by texts: they were built with inscribed bricks and nails, harbored numerous building inscriptions in their foundations, and inscribed objects stood within their walls. Despite this common presence of texts within the temple, cultic or liturgical compositions of the kind found in the series of ‘Ancient Sumerian’ are not really attested on architectural features or objects of Mesopotamian temples. Esaġil has not been excavated properly (see Pedersén 2021, 142–153), so we cannot know if it

³⁵ Debourse 2022a, 242–243.

³⁶ For a discussion of the reading of the title *aĥu-rabû* see Debourse (2022a, 222–228).

³⁷ Debourse 2022a, 171, 209–210 (with references to the different possibilities of reading this noun); the importance of the *written* text is also visible in the explicitly scribal characteristics contained in the manuscripts of ‘Ancient Sumerian’, including *Trennungszeichen* and scribal variants. The Eulogy makes use of colons and BM 41577 (NYF 5) has some scribal variants indicated by a *Trennungszeichen* (Debourse 2022a, 172 note on line iv 3’).

indeed contained written ritual texts or ritual recitations on its walls and objects. The question of the reality of a temple inscribed with the ‘Ancient Sumerian’ prayers is beside the point, however.³⁸ What matters for our discussion here is the fact that our texts create the impression that they were present everywhere in Esaġil, taking up an unprecedented role within the ritual space and process.

Important in light of this is the fact that there seems to be a tendency in the Late Babylonian period to give the written form of the ritual more authority than earlier.³⁹ Thus, for example, Emesal prayers recited by *kalû* priests are occasionally written with the determinative IM (referring to a clay tablet) in ritual texts and astronomical diaries (see Gabbay 2014, 229). This indicates the importance and authority of their written form, even though these compositions were mostly sung and performative in nature. In a similar vein, an astronomical diary dated to SE 41 (= 271 BCE), mentions the following ritual performance as occurring on the tenth day of month 12:⁴⁰

ITI.BI UD.10.KÁM [...] / [l¹⁰MA]Š.MAŠ.MEŠ u l¹⁰LAGAR.MEŠ ŠÁ é-sag-gil
né-pe-šú ŠÁ e-nu-m[a ...] / lib-bu-u šaṭ-ri ina pa-ni-šú DÙ-u’

“In this month, day 10 [...], the *āšipus* and *kalûs* of Esaġil performed the ritual of ‘When ...’ according to the written (object) in front of it”.

³⁸ The idea of the temple as inscribed with ritual texts, whether physically or conceptually, is not entirely far-fetched, and may have a parallel in the so-called “Admonitions to the Priests” in Ptolemaic Egypt (Leroux 2018; Assmann 1997 [2000], 185–190), even though the case in Egypt is of course much more substantial and is based on a longer and stronger tradition. These archaizing hieroglyphic texts were carved into temple walls and delineated ritual instructions, rules of purity, and other information that related to priestly duties. Their contents also directly reflected some of the cultic and liturgical practices that were performed in the spaces in which they were present. Modern scholars have adopted the terms “grammar of the temple” or “geographical liturgy” to describe this phenomenon (Derchain 1962). Another parallel may be found in early Jewish traditions: In the Mishnah (tractate Yoma, chapter 3:10), in a description of the manufacture and dedication of various ritual objects for the temple by different dignitaries, it is reported that “She (= Queen Helena, mother of King Monobaz of the northern Mesopotamian kingdom of Adiabene) also fashioned a golden tablet on which the Sotah portion (i. e., the passage in Numbers 5 on the ritual ordeal for a woman suspected of adultery) was written” (see Rosen-Zvi 2012, 158–160).

³⁹ In addition to the evidence enumerated below, note a tablet containing a list of ingredients to be used for ritual incense, which according to its colophon was copied from an alabaster tablet (BM 54069 rev. 1, see Jursa 2009, 148).

⁴⁰ ADART no. – 270B rev. 14’–17’ (Sachs/Hunger 1988); see Horowitz 1991, 75–77; Debourse 2022a, 191.

This report makes clear how the written form of the ritual acts as an authority for the performance of that ritual (and not the scholarly knowledge and tradition that this written text may reflect), important enough for it to be mentioned in this laconic report. It is not entirely clear what this written form of the ritual refers to: it may be the tablet according to which the priests performed their ritual, but it could also be another type of inscription. It is also not clear what “before it” refers to: The text written on the tablet before the text of their recitation? The text in front of one of the priests (i. e., “before him”)? Or, the inscription before a topographical feature or ritual component? If this refers to an inscription on a permanent part of the temple or on a stone placed within it, this would indicate an actual case of the presence of a text both performed and in its written form within a ritual.

Returning to the series ‘Ancient Sumerian’, the colophons mentioning inscriptions, stone tablets, and topographical features in the temple on which the text was written, indicate that in this series too there is an emphasis on the written form of textuality in rituals, specifically with respect to the recitations carried out in rituals. The written texts are the authority for the performance of the rituals and are physically encountered during the performance within the Esaġil temple. The perspective in the texts, as noted by Da Riva (2021, 210–211), is not that of someone instructing the priests, but that of an external observer, who watches and describes the acts performed by cultic personnel at specific moments in the ritual. Indeed, if the texts recited by the priests during the rituals were present not only orally, in their actual ritual performance, but also on the written objects surrounding them, then the ritual perspective is not only internal, from the eyes of the performer, but also external: the external observer of the ritual is the written texts themselves.

This perception, in which the agency of the written texts is given such importance, allowing the texts inscribed in the temple to observe what is going on physically within it (and in some aspect also to be part of the performance within it), differs from the typical perspective found in the more “standard” ritual texts in Mesopotamia, known especially from the seventh century BCE in Nineveh, but elsewhere and later as well (e. g., the Mīs pî ritual or building rituals, see Walker/Dick 2001; Ambos 2004). In these, usually earlier ritual texts, the focus is mostly limited to the actions of one priest, not a group of priests as in the later rituals, and the instructions are often addressed to this single priest in the second person: “you do this, you say that” (compare Ambos 2004, 173–176; Gabbay: forthcoming).

Unlike the Seleucid ritual texts, the “standard” ritual texts assign no significance to the written form of the text,

and the performer internalizes the rituals by studying their content.⁴¹ The text, as a written object, is not physically present with the performer at the time of performance, but rather it is internalized within him, in his mind, in his own identity. The text, at the time of performance, is not separated from him, nor does it have its own external perspective toward him, as is the case in the Seleucid texts. Thus, we see here two different perspectives: In the “standard” ritual texts, the texts are within the performer, they are internalized by him. But in the later Seleucid texts, the performer, or better, the group of performers, is physically enclosed in a space inscribed with written texts. In these later texts, the interplay between the actual performers and the textual performance, the blurring between the reality and the reflection, are not on the level of the individual, but on the level of a group, a community of priests working simultaneously, who are collectively internalized within texts that observe the priests within them.

But there is actually an extra twist to this confusion of realities. Not every detail in the ritual texts should be taken as reflecting an actual reality (Debourse 2022a, 369–370). The texts are ideological in nature: they establish an identity for a community of priests living in a changing world that disconnected them from their former social and political context (Jursa/Debourse 2020; Debourse 2022a, 399–403). So, reading that a priest should perform a ritual recitation according to a text that is written in a certain shrine, does not necessarily imply that he performed the ritual exactly as written in the text in front of him, and nor that there *was a physical text* in the shrine that told him what to perform and that observed him performing. This does not mean that we should not trust the content of the ritual texts – that would be too easy – but we should also not read the texts entirely literally, and we should bear in mind that there is a constant play here between the ideal and the real.

7 Conclusion

The series ‘Ancient Sumerian’ has its roots in an age-old cuneiform tradition but presents essential discursive innovations vis-à-vis that tradition. It consists of texts that were newly created during the Hellenistic period by members of

the priesthood of Bēl in Babylon. Each one of these texts revolves around aspects of the cult that took place in the Ešāgil temple. They share multiple other characteristics, including the use of obscure Sumerian, the presence of the Elder Brother priest, and a concern for kingship. Furthermore, a unique feature is that sections of these texts are presented as (copies of) inscriptions that were physically present in the Ešāgil temple in various forms. As described above, reading the series ‘Ancient Sumerian’ has the triple effect of leading one to imagine the physical temple, the rituals that took place in it, and the community of people who performed those rituals.

However, the image created by the series ‘Ancient Sumerian’ is misleading. At first sight, it seems to describe what it knows, and it has thus been taken to attest to the persistence of cultic traditions and architecture in Hellenistic Babylon (as it was interpreted also by Linssen 2004). Nevertheless, it is more likely that the series should be read as a marker of change instead and it is hard to tell in how far it relates to an actual reality. It is unclear, for example, if the Ešāgil temple was still fully functioning at Hellenistic Babylon, where it may have been partly replaced by the Temple of Daily Worship (*bit ūmakkal*, É.UD.1.KĀM; see Hackl 2021; Debourse 2020). The prominence of the priesthood, as it exudes from these texts, is also partly fiction, since they did not hold the power expressed in these rituals over contemporary kings. While this does not mean that no ritual reality underlies what is described in ‘Ancient Sumerian’ at all, it should be acknowledged that the series is not (merely) a ritual handbook, but first and foremost a textual representation of a new discourse.⁴²

This discourse can be read against the background of these texts’ context of creation. Like other literary and scholarly texts that were composed at this time, most notably those that belong to the so-called Late Babylonian Priestly Literature (Jursa/Debourse 2020), ‘Ancient Sumerian’ deals with the threats posed to the continuity of the traditional Babylonian cult due to the absence of native kingship, the loss of centrality, and the physical violence of constant warfare (Debourse 2022a, 403). What we see in the series ‘Ancient Sumerian’ can be described as a centralizing effort of a priesthood that felt its traditions come under threat.⁴³ By delineating the sanctuary space, ritual

⁴¹ This does not indicate that the “standard” texts (and the scholarly tradition associated with them) did not carry any authority (and indeed they did, as seen, for example, by the references to the authority of texts in Neo-Assyrian letters, usually in the context of divination; see Parpola 1993, XXVII–XXXIX); rather, the emphasis in the Seleucid texts is on this authority in relation to its *written* form on *objects*.

⁴² For definitions of discourse, see Pongratz-Leisten 2015, 21; Debourse 2022a, 337 note 1.

⁴³ Rhyder (2019, 8) defines centralization as “the structuring of power relations and social processes so that authority, decision making, and material resources are concentrated rather than dispersed. Inherent in the process of centralization is the ‘progressive subordination’ to central loci of power”.

practices, and the priestly community, a clear boundary was drawn around what was considered “true”, “correct”, and worthy of support.⁴⁴ The composition of new ritual texts served to normalize this new reality and at the same time justify it (see also Debourse 2022b). Moreover, the redactional effort of gathering texts that dealt with these themes within one series takes this one step further and can be seen as an attempt at stronger legitimization and affirmation of priestly authority – an effort that is underscored by the series’ title of ‘Ancient Sumerian’.

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⁴⁴ Compare to Rhyder’s (2019, 14) description of centralization as it is present in the Priestly Narratives in the Pentateuch (P): “The detailed description of the sanctuary space in the priestly traditions should be read not merely in terms of what it might reveal about the number of cultic sites deemed permissible in the ancient Israelite cult, but also in terms of how the priestly scribes use the description of space to solicit support for the cultic elites who claim an exclusive right to officiate within Yhwh’s sacred sanctuary, as well as for the ritual practices they consider legitimate within the Yahwistic cult. Moreover, the detailed ritual prescriptions in the priestly materials, even when not directly addressing the issue of where the Israelites must worship, are integral to constructing notions of what is central and peripheral to the Israelite cult and community, and to normalizing the hierarchies that are essential to negotiating centralization”.

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